

An improved blast-resistant rice cultivar for irrigated paddy in West Africa

S. S. Virmani, F. J. Sumo, and I. W. Buddenhagen, IITA/IDA-Liberia rice project, Suakoko, Liberia, and the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan, Nigeria

Among the several thousand cultivars introduced into West African programs since the early 1970s, the line IR1416-131-5, from the IRR1 cross Peta*4/TN1//Tetep, has proven to be both resistant to blast and excellent for irrigated conditions.

Until now, IR5 has been the most widely recommended and planted variety in irrigated swamps in Liberia. The swamps have been developed in rolling lowland terrain in a rain forest area where 1,800 to 3,000 mm of rainfall falls over an 8- to 10-month period.

Since its 1974 introduction, IR1416 has yielded better than IR5 in both wet and dry seasons in areas of Liberia where water control and soil conditions are good (see table). But IR5's yield in the wet season under poor water control or undefined imbalanced soil conditions remains superior. When sown directly at high seed rate and with fertilization (NPK, 150-50-70), IR1416 lodged moderately 2 weeks before maturity.

In Nigeria, IR1416 and BG90-2 from Sri Lanka are now the two main varieties grown at the high-technology Japanese/Nigerian irrigated rice project at Adani, Anambra state. This area is a derived savanna zone with about 1,400-mm rainfall from April to October. The objective of the project is to grow 10 t/ha per year from 2 crops — a goal reached on part of the area. Commercial yields of both IR1416 and BG90-2 have ranged from 4.5 to 5.5 t/ha. IR1416 is preferred for its blast resistance, its adaptability to direct sowing of pregerminated seeds, and its consistent performance in both dry and wet seasons. Compared with other rices, it is subject to less attack by the stem borer *Chilo zaccanius*.

IR1416 is a high-tillering spreading-type semidwarf (75–90 cm) of intermediate growth duration

Performance of IR1416 and IR5 in yield trials in Liberian irrigated inland valley swamps, 1974–77.

Year	Site	Yield (t/ha)		IR1416 yield (% of IR5)
		IR1416	IR5	
<i>Wet season, good management</i>				
1974	Suakoko	6.6	4.9	+64
1975	Suakoko	6.1	4.7	+30
1976	Suakoko	4.4	3.7	+21
1977	Voinjama	5.9	5.5	+8
	Mean	5.8	4.5	+32
<i>Wet season, poor water control^a</i>				
1975	Suakoko	3.4	3.4	+1
1977	Suakoko	3.4	5.1	-34
1977	Kolahun	3.9	5.8	-33
1977	Zlehtown	3.8	4.4	-13
	Mean	3.6	4.7	-26
<i>Dry season</i>				
1974	Suakoko	4.8	3.6	+32
1975	Foya	6.9	5.2	+33
1976	Suakoko	4.4	4.0	+10
1977	Suakoko	4.0	3.5	+15
	Mean	5.0	4.1	+23

^aNewly developed swamp, or land with imbalanced nutrition, or both.

(130–135 days). It has medium-long panicles and medium-slender grains (24 g/1,000-grain wt) that are more translucent and of better quality than those of IR5. In Liberia, IR1416 is especially preferred to IR5 because of its keeping quality after cooking. It has low levels of glume discoloration (dirty panicles), and good resistance to sheath blight, sheath rot, and leaf scald. IR1416 is moderately tolerant of iron toxicity, but susceptible to brown spot, caseworm, and rice yellow mottle virus. Blast did not attack it under the dryland, drought conditions at IITA that killed varieties such as IR5, BG90-2, and Brengut. In those trials, six major vertical genes, as indexed on japonica differentials, were present in the blast population.

In 1976, Liberia nominated IR1416 to the coordinated variety trials of the West Africa Rice Development Association (WARDA). It performed well under good management in Mauritania, Mali, Upper Volta, Sierra Leone, and Ivory Coast.

IR1416 is proposed for release in Liberia as Suakoko 12. It is considered most appropriate for West African paddy with good irrigation and with nontoxic soils — especially where current cultivars are subject to neck blast. It is used as a parent in IITA's hybridization program. ■

Induction of monogenic recessive male sterility in IR36 by ethyleneimine treatment

R. J. Singh and H. Ikehashi, Plant Breeding Department, International Rice Research Institute

To facilitate rapid recombination breeding and to save labor in the hybridization program, attempts were made to induce monogenic recessive male sterility in IR36 by use of ethyleneimine, a chemical mutagen. Dried IR36 seeds were treated with ethyleneimine at various concentrations (0.2%, 0.4%, 0.8%, 1.2%, and 1.6%) for 1 hour and 3 hours. The 0.2% concentration for 3 hours depressed germination by 69%; the 0.4% concentration for 1 hour depressed it by 30%. But the 0.2% for 1 hour gave 93% germination, similar to that of the control (99%). Seeds in other treatments did not germinate.

About 2,000 plants from treatments of 0.2% for 3 hours and 4% for 1 hour were planted in M₁. A single panicle was harvested from each M₁ plant. All M₁ plants produced M₂ pedigrees. Out of 1,954 M₂ lines of 12 plants each, 93 lines segregated for sterility and partial sterility. A single plant from each line was transferred from the field to the greenhouse for study of chromosomes, pollen fertility, and cross fertility of the female organ.

The meiotic pairing and pollen fertility studies of 93 M₂ lines revealed the following information.

Meiotic behavior	Pollen fertility range (%)	Lines (no.)
Reciprocal translocation	1.6–80.0	61
Triploid	0.9–2.1	2
Desynaptic plants	2.1–22.1	2
Normal meiosis	80.0	13
Meiosis not studied	33.0–89.0	6
Normal meiosis	0.0–4.0	4
Not identified		5
Total		93

Four male-sterile lines had excellent crossability with IR36. No seed set was observed after selfing but some seeds were obtained from sterile plants produced by outcrossing. All the M₃ plants were fertile. But when pollination

Segregation of four M₄ male-sterile lines. IRRI, 1978.

Designated male-sterile line	Pedigree	Fertile (no.)	Sterile (no.)	Total (no.)	(X ²) ^a 3:1
ms-a	E2-3-10	209	80	289	1.00
	E2-3-10	207	75	282	0.38
	E2-3-11	214	83	357	0.58
	E2-3-11	349	108	457	0.45
Total		1039	346	1385	0.00
ms-b	E2-538-6	199	69	268	0.08
ms-c	E6-953-10	196	58	254	0.64
ms-d	E6-1335-5	217	64	281	0.74

^a X² = table value for a df (5%) = 3.84.

was controlled, the F₁ plants were completely fertile. That indicates the

recessive nature of male sterility, which was also confirmed in the M₄, as all the

Isolation of tall and dwarf seedlings of rice

J. Begum, Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal, India

In the segregating populations of dwarf-tall crosses, isolation of the dwarf seedlings from the tall in the nursery offers certain testing advantages. Failure to separate the dwarfs from the tall may ultimately result in extinction of the dwarf types or suppression of their performance. Therefore, preliminary tests were conducted to determine the association of certain morphological characters to aid in the selection of the dwarf types in the nursery. Eighty pure line rice varieties of diverse sources were

tested during boro (summer).

The number of leaves at 25 days after sowing (X₂) and at 35 days (X₃), and seedling length at 25 days after sowing (Y₁) and at 35 days (Y₂) were recorded. X₂ and X₃ were correlated with mature plant height (X₁). A significant positive association between X₁ and seedling characters X₂, X₃, Y₁, Y₂ was found (see table). X₂ and X₃ were also highly significant and positively correlated with Y₁ and Y₂. In 1970, W. L. Chang reported that seedling length was positively correlated with plant height, especially during early growth.

The results indicated that the dwarf types will have shorter seedlings that produce fewer leaves. Therefore, the

four male-sterile lines segregated in a 3-1 ratio (see table).

Incomplete panicle exertion was observed for lines ms-a, ms-b, and ms-d, but ms-c showed normal panicle exertion. That indicates that spikelets of line ms-c have a greater chance than the three other male-sterile lines of receiving pollen from the neighboring fertile plants. A single panicle per male-sterile plant was harvested to study the amount of outcrossing in male-sterile lines. Outcrossing was maximum for ms-c (33.6%), followed by ms-d (32.5%), ms-b (29.8%), and ms-a (14.8%). ■

number of leaves and elongation rate of the seedlings should be considered when separating the dwarfs from the tall in the nursery.

Correlation (r) values between mature plant height (X₁) and number of seedling leaves (X₂ and X₃) and seedling length (Y₁ and Y₂). Chinsurah, West Bengal, India.

Characters	r value
X ₁ X ₂	0.9730**
X ₁ X ₃	0.9637**
X ₁ Y ₁	0.9792**
X ₁ Y ₂	0.9700**
X ₂ Y ₁	0.9891**
X ₂ Y ₂	0.9658**
X ₃ Y ₁	0.9531**
X ₃ Y ₂	0.9818**

**Significant at 1% level of probability.

Four new rice varieties released in Nepal

B. B. Shahi, national rice coordinator, National Rice Improvement Program, Parwanipur Agriculture Station, Birganj, Nepal

After intensive research on promising genotypes in Nepalese research stations and in farmers' fields for more than 4 years, the national seed committee has released 4 varieties for the tarai, inner tarai, and equivalent climatic regions of Nepal.

For the chaite dhan season (early crop, Mar-Jun)

1. *Laxami*, formerly IR206 1-628-1-6-4-3, from the cross IR833-6-2-1-1//IR1561-149-1/IR1737. The line was introduced into Nepal through the

International Rice Yield Nursery-Early (IRYN-E) in 1975. It matures in 111 days – one of the earliest cultivars released.

2. *Durga*, formerly IET2938 (Jaya//IR8/2*Latisail). Bred in India, the line was introduced into Nepal through the IRYN-Medium duration nursery in 1974.

For the barkhe dhan season (normal monsoon)

3. *Janaki*, formerly BG90-2 (Peta*3/TNI/Remadja) was developed in Sri Lanka and introduced into Nepal through the IRYN-M in 1975.

4. *Subitri*, formerly IR2071-124-6-4 (IR1561-228-1/IR1737//CR94-13), was introduced into Nepal through India's initial evaluation trial in 1975.

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN. Duplicate prints of photos and illustrations are available to media on request from the office of Information Services, IRRI. Persons who wish additional details of information presented in IRRN should write directly to the authors.